

HPG ED

HPC-ED.GITHUB.IO

- **Project Goals:**

- Make existing HPC Training and Education materials more findable
- Create a federated catalog that can be easily searched
- Facilitate community use of project tools and provide feedback

- Project site: <https://hpc-ed.github.io>

- Documentation: <https://github.com/HPC-ED/HPC-ED.github.io/wiki>